

A Study on English Listening Challenges For English-majored Students at HUFU

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Abstract

One of the essential skills in our daily lives is listening skill. It is very important to help people understand and be able to communicate with others around them. For many years, listening skill has always made it difficult for foreign language learners because learners do not have a learning environment with native speakers. According to the survey for 30 students at HUFU for third-year English-majored students with questionnaires, many reasons for learning listening skill like how students learn by themselves, a few other factors such as lecturers, the aircraft sounds, and the school's sound system. Therefore, students and lecturers will seek to overcome English listening skill challenges. The results of the paper indicated that there are several reasons for challenges in learning listening skill. To talk about this issue, the difficulty of learning to listen is that students do not listen enough times and have problems such as the speed of the speech, lack of vocabulary, incorrect pronunciation, and distraction when listening. Teachers play an important role in teaching step-by-step students to approach effective learning.

Keywords: Listening ; listening skill; students; challenges;problems

1. Introduction

Listening skill is very important to everyone and helps learners to communicate well (Moulesong, 2010). It is also an input skill to understand languages. To speak well, people need to listen well (Kaufmann, 2019). Therefore, if not listening clearly, not for effective communication. As a result, English language learners need good listening skill. Within the scope of this article, the primary purpose of the study is to find challenges in listening skill of English-majored students at Ho Chi Minh City University of Food Industry (HUFU) and give some methods to improve. This research focuses on how to improve listening skill and how to solve some problems for all students; especially English-majored students belong to foreign language faculty.

2. Literature review

2.1. Definition of listening:

Howatt and Dakin (1974) defined that listening is the ability to identify and understand what others are saying. This involves understanding a speaker's accent or pronunciation, his grammar and his vocabulary, and grasping his meaning.

2.2. The importance of listening skill:

Listening is one of the indispensable skills to life that defined as “skills which can provide you with a better perspective on life, skills which can allow you to maintain a higher awareness of both yourself and the world around you”. In the process of learning

English as a second language, listening skill is very important. Besides listening to be able to communicate in real life and learners also have to listen to understand the lesson so that they can pass the tests in their class. If the learners do not listen well, it will lead to non-understanding of the content and not easy to get high scores. Therefore, students need to be aware of how to listen effectively.

Basically, the surrounding things that you know are learned by listening. Listening becomes a habit - as well as being comfortable and effective when listening, your brain receives the sound and processes information easily so that you can understand what you hear. Listening skill is an important key to all effective communication, if the ability to hear is not good, it may be missed information from the speaker and easily misunderstood. For instance, when communicating with someone, you need to hear and understand what the speaker is saying to you and to say exactly what you want.

2.3. Learners' problems in learning the listening skill:

According to Yagang (1994), there are 4 factors that make it difficult to learn the listening skill: the message, the speaker, the listener, and the physical setting. Most of the students find it difficult to listen to a message without viewing the script in the material. They need time to read the script before they start listening to the lesson because they cannot keep up with the speed of speech. It becomes a barrier when learners learn the listening skill. Moreover, vocabulary and pronunciation are also challenging that students face. When listening to a topic, students encounter unknown words, they do not focus on listening to think about that words, and they may miss some information from the speaker. Besides, learners often find it not interesting and boring with learning the listening skill.

3. Method

3.1 Identify subsections

In the study, the purpose of finding problems that makes it difficult to learn listening skill which is carried out in the following 4 steps:

*Step 1: Creating the questionnaire related to students' challenges in listening skill and finding participants

*Step 2: Collecting the data from the recorded information.

*Step 3: Analyzing the collected data

*Step 4: Writing the research paper

The questionnaires for students that consist of 10 questions. Some students answered about their personal information and ideas through the questions.

3.2 Participants

The participants were 30 third-year English-majored students in the Faculty of Foreign Languages at HUFU. The object of the study was 30 third-year students when

they were in the second semester of the academic year 2019-2020 at HUFİ. Most students have studied English for more than 10 years. However, according to the high school curriculum, they do not often practice English skills such as listening skill because teachers only teach grammar and vocabulary for students. When students go to university environment, HUFİ, for example, learners have to face many challenges in learning English.

3.2 Data collection instrument

3.3.1. The survey questionnaire

The questions were designed by the researcher to summarize and analyze the collected data. The questionnaires for students included 8 questions designated in the two research questions, and the student questionnaire was sent to 30 third-year English students at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, HUFİ to find information for two research questions. Of the 10 questions, the first part is designed to collect student information, the second part questions to find out some English listening methods for the third year student of Foreign Language Faculty, HUFİ.

In order to ensure the accuracy of this survey, the things need to know and the purposes have been explained before students take the survey questions. Then, students from 3 classes take a quick survey to complete the survey through the survey questionnaire.

3.3.2. Data collection procedures

In the study, the data is collected from third-year students of Faculty of Foreign Languages. The purpose is to collect data on the issues of learning English listening skill by sending the survey questionnaires to 30 students.

Then, the results of the survey shown that a brief overview of the difficulties students face in listening skill.

4 Finding and Discussion

4.1 Real situation of students

The participants in this research are 30 English-majored students from 3 classes and they are currently the third-year in the Faculty of Foreign Languages at HUFİ. In this quick survey, students take short and quick surveys through direct in-class surveys. Students are answered questions by choosing the best answer from their point of view.

Here is the result from the survey

Which skill do you think is the most difficult in English?	Rate (%)
a. Listening	18 students (60%)

b.Speaking	5 students (16.67%)
c.Reading	4 students (13.33%)
d.Writing	3 students (10%)

Table 1. The survey result of students on the difficulty level of skills in English

The table 1 shows that the survey results of students on the difficulty level of skills in English, 5 students(16.67%) think that speaking skill is difficult, 4 students(13.33%) give that reading skill is not easy and only 3 students (10%) say that writing skill is difficult. Most students (about 18 students in 30 students) accounting for 60% think that listening skill is a difficult subject to them.

According to the collected information, many students failed their tests of listening skill. Below is the statistical result from the questionnaires

	Have you ever failed your listening test?	Percentage (%)
a.	Never	4 students (13.33%)
b.	Once	9 students (30%)
c.	Twice	8 students (26.67%)
d.	Three times	5 students (16.67%)
e.	More than three	4 students (13, 33%)

Table 2. The result of students on the listening test

The table 2 shows that the result of students on the listening test. In this table, it indicates that up to 86.67% of the participants failed in their listening test. Therefore, learners feel that listening skill is difficult in four skills. Students need to practice listening for a long time to be able to listen better in the future. In addition, self-study is also an important factor to help them in the process of learning a foreign language. According to the survey results, however, the time for self-study at home is not much. There is 73.33% of them sometimes self-study listening at home, 16.67% (rarely), and 10% (never). But practicing regularly helps learners gain confidence in their listening ability. Also, listening needs a method and purpose to be highly effective for each listening.

4.2 The difficulties in learning listening skill

4.2.1. The problems from learners

Problems	Never	Sometimes	Often	Always
Making prediction what the speaker talks about		36.67%	30%	33.33%

Guessing unknown words while listening		20%	33.33%	46.67%
Recognizing main points	23.33%	16.67%	33.33%	26.67%

Table 3. The problems from learners

The author designed the survey to find out the problems that make it difficult for learners, and the result shows that predicting what the speaker will say about something is a problem with 30%(often) and 33.33%(always). In the lesson, the lecturer gives some suggestions before listening to make it easier for the learners to visualize and predict the ideas of the speech. In addition, giving an overview of questions related to the topic for students to answer. Because students often get used to listening to each word individually, they do not focus on listening based on the cues of the speech to guess what the speaker will say the next ideas. On the other hand, students' understanding of vocabulary is also a problem because the vocabulary is very diverse. While listening people often have the habit of trying to understand every word (Case, 2008). There is up to 80% of participants often do it in listening lessons. It can cause learners to miss the next speaker's ideas when encountering unknown words. Another problem is that students do not recognize the main points.

4.2.2. *The problems from listening material*

Problems	Never	Sometimes	Often	Always
Unfamiliar topics		63.33%	30%	6.67%
Different accents		23.33%	46.67%	30%
Authentic material		10%	66.67%	23.33%
Colloquial words	10%	36.67%	40%	13.33%
Speed of speech		30%	53.33%	16.67%
Linking words		16.67%	13.33%	70%
Ungrammatical sentences		53.33%	46.67%	
Hesitation	23.33%	46.67%	30%	
Long listening	20%	50%	30%	

Table 4. The problems from listening material

According to the above statistical results, there are 63.33% (sometimes) and 36.67% (often and always) of participants have difficulty encountering topics that are strange to them because the coursebook can have many topics that cover many things in life.

They often feel confused when listening to a topic that appears new words, phrases, and terms. Therefore, learners need to practice listening to different types and topics to be more confident when listening to a new topic.

Another problem in listening is the accent because there are many different types of accents. If the learners are accustomed to listening to British or American accents, it can be difficult when the speaker is another accent. For example, the learners listen to the Indian accent, they will have difficulty understanding what the speaker is saying.

The authentic material is also a point that makes it difficult for students. Students often study with formal English books that do not contain lots of colloquial words, expressions, and slang. Therefore, if learners listen to the informal conversations, they may not understand what they are listening to.

Besides, there are other issues like the speed of the speech, linking words, ungrammatical sentences, and hesitation of the speakers. Most students think that these things make it difficult for them to recognize words when they listen to a topic that has linking words or the speed of speech is fast. Furthermore, people use ungrammatical structure because of anxiety and hesitation and can skip parts of the sentence or add something redundant so this is a challenge to the listener's understanding. There is up to 46.67% of participants who have faced these problem. In addition, the long listening text is also considered a barrier for students. According to the survey results, 80% of participants found it difficult to listen to long text. Because they could not remember much of the ideas and could be distracting, which did not bring good results. The best way for learners to listen to long texts is note-taking skills so that they can take notes of the main ideas and important information of the text. This will help students recall the information later. Learners can also use symbols when taking notes. It is very useful and helps to make notes faster.

4.2.3. *The problems from physical settings*

Problems	Never	Sometimes	Often	Always
Noise		10%	26.67%	63.33%
Poor tape quality		46.67%	30%	23.33%
Poor equipments		23.33%	50%	26.67%

Table 5. The problems from physical settings

From the table 5, it can be seen that the noise directly affects the learners. According to statistics, more than 60% of participants have been affected by the noise. While they are concentrating on listening, suddenly there is the noise coming from outside the classroom or the noise of the plane sounds. It makes learners feel uncomfortable and distracted when listening, which gives students poor results in listening and can not complete the tasks of the lesson. On the other hand, the tapes or disks used for the learning process is also a problem. This means that it is used many times or too old to cause poor quality. Another obstacle for students to listen to is that poor

equipment. Currently, the school has arranged a number of modern labs. For effective listening, learners need to study in such rooms so that they can concentrate higher without being disturbed by the noise.

5. Recommendation

To improve listening skill better than before, students should learn how to change their listening habits and improve their basic knowledge. Students need to practice English every day by listening to an English song, watching English news or reading English books, ... According to recent research results, students often listen to word by word and have not grasped the focus of what the speaker says. As a result, they often find it difficult and distracting. Therefore, in the process of listening, students need to identify the main ideas and keywords of the speech and use note-taking techniques to take notes. However, it needs the support of teachers to help and guide students step by step listening: pre-listening, while-listening and post-listening. In addition, teachers will give some tips on extra practice exercises so that students can self-study at home. And here are some ways to solve the problems of listening by (Willis, 1981): Predict what people are going to talk about; guessing at unknown words or phrases without panicking; using one's own knowledge of the subject to help one understand, understanding inferred information.

6. Conclusion

In short, within the scope of this article, it has been shown that listening is one of the most necessary skills in learning any language, which can help learners to confidently communicate in real life. During the course of the study, the author surveyed some students at the FFL, HUFU. As a result, students have some difficulties with listening skill such as learners do not spend much time to listen and the way of learning is not very effective. It can hardly help learners improve their listening skill. Also, factors from the physical setting and the material used for listening are also an issue. Therefore, learners need to make more listening efforts to improve their listening skill like listening in their own language. In addition, teachers who help students recognize and perform tasks correctly while listening. The issues and suggestions that the research contributes to helping students improve their skill in the process of learning English at the Faculty of Foreign Languages, HUFU.

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Abbreviations

- (1)HUFU: Ho Chi Minh city University of Food Industry
- (2)FFL: Faculty of Foreign Languages

Appendix

Dear all,

I am doing a research paper entitled "A study on English listening challenges for English-majored students at HUFU".The purpose of the survey questionnaire is to find out the challenges students face in the listening skill. Therefore, I need you to complete this survey so that I can collect the data in the best way. Thanks for your help!

Part I: Personal information
1.What is your gender? a. Male b. Female c. Other
2.What is your class? a.08DHAV1

b.08DHAV2 c.08DHAV3
3.Which skill do you think is the most difficult in English? a.Listening b.Speaking c.Reading d.Writing
Part II: Overview of listening skill
4.Have you ever failed your listening test? (choose the best answer) a. Never b. Once c. Twice d. Three times e. More than three
5.How often do you self-study listening at home? (choose the best answer) a. Never b. Rarely c. Sometimes d. Often
6.How do you self-study at home? (you can choose more than one) a. Listen to English songs b. Listen to tapes or disks of the syllabus in university c. Listen to news in English d. Other: _____
7.What do you do before listening? (you can choose more than one) a. Go through the questions and guess what the topic is about b. Nothing to do just ready to listen c. Guess the content of the listening d. Ask about the new words e. Read the task instruction

8. What do you do while you are listening for the first time? (choose the best answer)

- a. Listen to word by word
- b. Listen for the detail information
- c. Focus on the new words
- d. Other: _____

9. What do you do if you cannot understand words or phrases while listening? (Choose the best answer)

- a. Ignore it and keep on listening
- b. Try to guess its meaning
- c. Feel depressed and cannot listen anymore

10. How often do you encounter these following problems? (Put a tick in the appropriate column)

Problems	Never	Some times	Often	Always
Making prediction what the speaker talks about				
Guessing unknown words while listening				
Unfamiliar topics				
Lacking of background knowledge				
Speed of speech				
Recognizing main points				
Linking words				
Authentic material				
Ungrammatical sentences				
Different accents				
Colloquial words				
Hesitation				
Long listening text				
Noises				

Poor tape quality				
The poor equipment's				